

RENAISSANCE survey on renewable energy and community-based solutions
[English]

1. WELCOME

Dear participant,

RENAISSANCE project developed the following questionnaire to assess social acceptance of renewable energies and innovative community-based production and consumption models.

We invite you to complete this survey to collect your experience and views regarding:

- General awareness of environmental and energy issues
- Awareness of european, national and local policies
- Individual decision making
- Perceived risks and benefits
- Impact of social context on energy supply choices
- Acceptance of innovative technologies and services

The survey is anonymous and will take approximately 20 minutes to complete.

ABOUT RENAISSANCE PROJECT

This survey is being conducted as part of the RENAISSANCE Project funded by the European Union. RENAISSANCE project works to deliver a community-driven, scalable and replicable approach for implementing new business models and technologies that support clean production and shared distribution of energy in local communities. In this way, it supports the shift from technology-driven to consumer-driven approaches.

ABOUT YOUR PARTICIPATION

Your participation in this study is fully voluntary and all data collected will be treated confidentially. The research outputs resulting from this work will only include collated data, without the possibility for anyone to identify your individual answers. The survey does not require you to provide any information that could identify you personally (e.g., your name). If, whilst completing the survey, you wish to withdraw, please just close the browser without submitting your answers.

By submitting this form:

- you confirm that you are at least 18 years old, have read and understood this consent form.
- you agree to participate in this research study and are happy for your anonymized answers to be included in our analysis and resulting from it research publications.
- you agree that we will process your data in line with our [Privacy Policy](#).

If you have any questions or would like to know more about the RENAISSANCE project results, please contact us at info@renaissance-h2020.eu

Visit the RENAISSANCE project at www.renaissance-h2020.eu

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2. BACKGROUND INFORMATION

1. What is your age?

- 18-24
- 25-34
- 35-44
- 45-54
- 55-64
- 65+

2. What is your gender?

- Female
- Male
- Other

3. In what country did you mainly reside in the last five years?

4. In what city, town or village? (can be also a generic region or area)

5. In what country did you live most of your lifetime? (answer if different from previous question)

6. How would you describe the context you live in:

- Thinly populated area
- Intermediate density area
- Densely populated area

7. What is your highest level of education?

- Primary school
- Middle school/Lower secondary
- Secondary school/Upper secondary
- Other (please specify)
- College diploma/Bachelor degree or higher
- I prefer not to answer

8. Among the following energy consumer types, which one best represents your current position?

- Tenant/Leasehold consumer
- Household consumer
- Landowner consumer
- Other (please specify)
- Public service consumer
- Local enterprise/Commercial consumer
- Industrial consumer

9. What is your annual net income?

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3. Background Info

10. Household composition:

Among the following options, please select those that best apply to your current position.

- At least one member of the household is more than 60 years old.
- At least one member of the household is less than 12 years old.
- At least one member of the household is unemployed.
- At least one member of the household needs extra care for health reasons.
- None of the above.

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4. Background Info

11. Roughly how many full-time employees currently work for your organization?

- 1-10
- 11-50
- 51-200
- 201-500
- 501-1,000
- 1,001-5,000
- 5,001-10,000
- 10,000+

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5. AWARENESS 1/3

12. Currently, energy is produced kilometers away from its point of delivery. Such a distribution grid results in a loss of efficiency.

In your opinion, how much of the energy produced in Europe is lost during this process, on average?

- 0% - 5%
- 5% - 10%
- 10% - 15%
- 15% - 20%
- 20% - 50%
- 50% - 70%
- 70% - 90%

13. **Among the following energy sources, please select the ones you think are renewable.**

- | | |
|--|--------------------------------------|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Biofuels | <input type="checkbox"/> Natural Gas |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Biomass | <input type="checkbox"/> Oil |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Coal | <input type="checkbox"/> Nuclear |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Geothermal | <input type="checkbox"/> Solar |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Hydroelectric | <input type="checkbox"/> Wind |

14. **Among the following types of household energy usage, which one do you think is the most energy-consuming?**

- Cooking
- Lighting
- Space cooling (air conditioning)
- Space heating
- Water heating
- Appliances

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6. AWARENESS 2/3

15. Among the following global issues, which ones are of most concern in your opinion?

	very low	low	moderately high	high	very high
Climate change	<input type="radio"/>				
Crime	<input type="radio"/>				
Economic situation	<input type="radio"/>				
Infectious diseases	<input type="radio"/>				
Overpopulation	<input type="radio"/>				
Poverty	<input type="radio"/>				
Terrorism	<input type="radio"/>				
Unemployment	<input type="radio"/>				
Violence/War	<input type="radio"/>				

16. Among the following environmental issues, which ones are of most concern in your opinion, on a global scale?

	very low	low	moderately high	high	very high
Acidification of rain and oceans	<input type="radio"/>				
Air pollution	<input type="radio"/>				
Rising of global temperatures	<input type="radio"/>				
Extreme weather conditions	<input type="radio"/>				
Environmental resource exploitation (Intensive fishing and breeding, intensive mining, intensive extraction of fossil fuels, deforestation)	<input type="radio"/>				
Loss of biodiversity	<input type="radio"/>				
Pollution of rivers and seas	<input type="radio"/>				
Soil pollution	<input type="radio"/>				
Traffic congestion	<input type="radio"/>				
Waste disposal	<input type="radio"/>				

17. In your opinion, how important is the overall impact of the current energy production model on the environmental issues mentioned above?

- Not at all important
- Not so important
- Somewhat important
- Very important
- Extremely important

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7. AWARENESS 3/3

18. In your opinion, the increased use and expansion of renewable energy at a global scale is:

- | | |
|-------------------------------------|-------------------------------------|
| <input type="radio"/> Very negative | <input type="radio"/> Positive |
| <input type="radio"/> Negative | <input type="radio"/> Very positive |
| <input type="radio"/> Neutral | |

19. In your opinion, the local production of renewable energy is:

- | | |
|-------------------------------------|-------------------------------------|
| <input type="radio"/> Very negative | <input type="radio"/> Positive |
| <input type="radio"/> Negative | <input type="radio"/> Very positive |
| <input type="radio"/> Neutral | |

20. In your opinion, who should take the first step towards renewable energy production? (up to 3 choices)

- Energy distributors
- Energy producers
- National policy makers and regulators
- Regional policy makers and regulators
- Local communities and citizens' associations
- Environmental groups
- Individual citizens
- Other (please specify)

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8. NATIONAL AND LOCAL POLICIES 1/2

21. Are you aware of any recent initiatives, from your local administration, to support a more sustainable energy production and consumption?

- There are no initiatives.
- I am not aware of any initiatives.
- I know there are some initiatives but I cannot recall the specific name.
- I know there are some initiatives, I could name them but I do not recall their specific content.
- I know there are some initiatives and I know their names and contents.

please specify a name or link

22. In your opinion, in which decision-making process/es should local administrations involve local communities?

- Siting issues (property value, disruption of place).
- Environmental impact.
- Other (please specify)
- Health and safety concerns.
- Societal risks and benefits.

23. Please state your level of agreement with the following statements regarding your local energy policies.

Strongly disagree Moderately disagree Neither agree nor disagree Moderately agree Strongly agree

The initiatives from my local administration are ensuring fair and transparent decision-making processes.

My local community has been involved in administrative decisions related to future energy policies.

24. The directive "CLEAN ENERGY FOR ALL EUROPEANS" obliges Member States to ensure a more competitive, consumer-centered, flexible and non-discriminatory EU electricity market with market-based supply prices. It strengthens existing customer rights, introduces new ones, and provides a framework for energy communities of prosumers. In the context of renewable energies, a prosumer is someone that both consumes and produces the energy, mainly based on distributed systems installed in households or within mini-grid community networks.

Were you already aware of the existence of such directive?

- Yes
- No

25. In your opinion, how important are such directives for building effective strategies towards a sustainable energy system?

- | | |
|--|---|
| <input type="radio"/> Not at all important | <input type="radio"/> Very important |
| <input type="radio"/> Not so important | <input type="radio"/> Extremely important |
| <input type="radio"/> Somewhat important | <input type="radio"/> I don't know |

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9. NATIONAL AND LOCAL POLICIES 2/2

In this section of the survey you will be asked to evaluate four potential scenarios for the future energy market (Question 26-27-28-29).

Each scenario is described through the following parameters:

- Location of assets
- Size
- Investment
- Energy trading model
- Decision making process

In all scenarios exclusively local renewable energy is produced, stored or traded. Considering your local context, please star-rank them from the most desirable condition to the least.

Read carefully all four scenarios available before proceeding.

26. PROSUMER MODEL

Location of assets: prosumers are incentivized to install production systems in their own property.

Size: small sized system (e.g. solar panels on rooftops, small scale wind or geothermal systems).

Investment: prosumers invest in their own energy production system for own consumption.

Energy trading model: energy is produced with the aim of collecting revenues; surplus energy is directly fed into the grid and remunerated by the central grid system operator for a set tariff.

Decision making process: the involvement in decision making is low. Beyond from the initial choices about investment and amount of energy traded, there is no power of decision on any other matter related to the energy production, consumption or trading. The amount of revenues collected by the prosumer depends on the amount of energy power installed.

27. OTHER KINDS OF ORGANIZED PROSUMER MODEL, P2P, VIRTUAL POWER PLANT

Location of assets: prosumers are incentivized to install production systems in their own property.

Size: small sized system (e.g. solar panels on rooftops, small scale wind or geothermal systems).

Investment: prosumers invest in their own energy production system for own consumption.

Energy trading model: energy is produced mainly to cover own consumption needs. Surplus energy is traded directly to other consumers (e.g. the neighbors) or aggregated and sold to the wholesale energy market.

Decision making process: the involvement in decision making is limited. Since energy peers or groups of prosumers have an active role in the energy market, a certain power on tariff setting may emerge when selling energy to aggregators or wholesale market.

28. ESCO

Location of assets: the energy supply company owns the energy plants that are dislocated locally.

Size: medium to large scale renewable energy plant.

Investment: large investments from energy supply company owners are required. End-users are contributing to the return of investment simply buying energy from the company.

Energy trading model: energy is produced with the aim of collecting revenues. Energy produced by the energy supply company is sold to the wholesale market. End-users pay their bill according to their current energy contract.

Decision making process: there is no involvement in decision making. Choices are taken by the management of involved actors and decisions follow the top-down flow.

29. ENERGY COMMUNITY

Location of assets: local renewable energy plants are installed in community member own property and/or dislocated in local available areas through a community decision process.

Size: small sized systems and/or medium scale systems.

Investment: requires a shared investments from all members of the community. The amount of energy production assets installed cover the overall community consumption.

Energy trading model: energy is produced to cover community consumption needs. Surplus energy is aggregated and sold to the wholesale market, directly to other consumers or stored for future demand. Revenues are distributed among community members in a form of retribution or new investments.

Decision making: the involvement in decision making is high. All members of the community have the right to vote on issues concerning the use of collected revenues, new investments and market strategy.

30. Do you want to comment or add something concerning the above scenarios?

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10. INDIVIDUAL DECISION MAKING

Perceived costs, facilitating conditions, local context

31. Are you aware of any public incentives or facilitating measures in your country supporting consumers transition to renewable energy sources?

- | | |
|--|---|
| <input type="radio"/> There are no incentives or facilitating measures. | <input type="radio"/> I know there are some incentives or facilitating measures and I know what they are about in general terms. |
| <input type="radio"/> I am not aware of any incentives or facilitating measures. | <input type="radio"/> I know there are some incentives or facilitating measures and I try to collect information to know more about them. |
| <input type="radio"/> I know there are some incentives or facilitating measures but I do not know what they are about. | |

32. In your opinion, the amount of incentives or facilitating measures supporting consumers' transitions to renewable energy sources in your country are:

- | | |
|---|------------------------------------|
| <input type="radio"/> None at all | <input type="radio"/> A lot |
| <input type="radio"/> A little | <input type="radio"/> A great deal |
| <input type="radio"/> A moderate amount | |

33. Please state you level of agreement with the following statements regarding costs of energy.

Strongly disagree Moderately disagree Neutral Moderately agree Strongly agree

Using existing renewable energy technologies may result in a less expensive bill for the consumers who adopt them.

Using renewable energy technologies may result in a reduction of overall energy costs for the whole society.

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11. PERCEIVED RISKS

34. State your level of agreement with the following statement:

"I would switch to renewable only energy providers if..."

	Very unlikely	Unlikely	Neither likely nor unlikely	Likely	Very likely
"...it would result in a less expensive bill"	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
"...it would result in an unvaried bill"	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
"...it would result in a slightly higher bill"	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

35. Imagine you have the possibility to switch to a renewable energy only provider for your own energy supply.

Among the following risks, please rank the ones which would prevent you from taking such decision (from the most impactful (#1) to the least (#4)):

Low maturity of service and/or market resulting in lower quality of service.

Hidden or unknown costs.

Too much hassle to switch.

Transparency issues and distributive justice.

36. Imagine that you have the possibility to install a small renewable energy production system in your property.

Among the following risks, please rank the ones which would prevent you from taking such decision (from the most impactful (#1) to the least (#6)):

Safety (e.g. potential adverse events related to malfunctions and/or damaged systems).

High maintenance costs.

Aesthetical (e.g. disruption of place, impact on landscape, property value).

Environmental (e.g. impact on biodiversity).

Health (e.g. glare effect, noise and infrasound, electromagnetism).

Too much hassle to switch.

37. Imagine that a renewable energy production plant was going to be built in your village/neighborhood for collective consumption of your local community.

Among the following risks, please rank the ones which would prevent you from accepting such decision (from the most impactful (#1) to the least (#8)):

Safety (e.g. potential adverse events related to malfunctions and/or damaged systems).

Low maturity of service and/or market resulting in lower quality of service.

Hidden or unknown costs.

Too much hassle to switch.

Environmental (e.g. impact on biodiversity).

Aesthetical (e.g. disruption of place, impact on landscape, property value).

Health (e.g. glare effect, noise and infrasound, electromagnetism).

Transparency issues and distributive justice.

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12. PERCEIVED BENEFITS

38. Imagine you have the possibility to switch to a renewable energy only provider for your own energy supply.

Among the following reasons, please rank the ones which would convince you to take such decision (from the most convincing to the least):

Social benefits (e.g. increased local employment, more qualified "green jobs").

Environmental benefits (e.g. lower emissions).

Economic benefits (e.g. lower energy costs, potential income).

Community awareness (e.g. higher chances to learn about renewable energy).

Higher resilience in case of an energy crisis / Higher capacity to overcome an energy crisis.

Community engagement (higher involvement in choices, higher control over energy production).

39. Imagine that you have the possibility to become a prosumer by installing an individual renewable energy production system in your property.

Among the following reasons, please rank the ones which would convince you to take such decision (from the most convincing to the least):

Environmental benefits (e.g lower emissions).

Economic benefits (e.g. lower energy costs, potential income).

Community engagement (higher involvement in choices, higher control over energy production).

Higher resilience in case of an energy crisis / Higher capacity to overcome an energy crisis.

Community awareness (e.g. higher chances to learn about renewable energy).

Social benefits (e.g. increased local employment, more qualified "green jobs").

40. Imagine that a renewable energy production plant was built in your village/neighborhood for the collective consumption of your local community.

Among the following reasons, please rank the ones which would convince you to buy energy from your local community plant, i.e. switching to a renewable energy only collective local production model (from the most convincing to the least):

Social benefits (ie.g. increased local employment, more qualified "green jobs").

Environmental benefits (e.g lower emissions).

Economic benefits (e.g. lower energy costs, potential income).

Community engagement (higher involvement in choices, higher control over energy production).

Higher resilience in case of an energy crisis / Higher capacity to overcome an energy crisis.

Community awareness (e.g. higher chances to learn about renewable energy).

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13. SOCIAL CONTEXT

41. Would you ask for advice before switching to a different energy supply service?

- Very unlikely Likely
 Unlikely Very likely
 Neither likely nor unlikely

42. Would you adopt renewable energies if you realized the majority of your neighbors are doing so?

- Very unlikely Likely
 Unlikely Very likely
 Neither likely nor unlikely

43. Among the following platforms, please select those you would use the most to support your decision making when switching to a different energy supply service (up to 3 answers):

- TV, radio and newspaper
 Internet and social media
 Academic journal or publications from experts
 Environmental associations, NGOs
 Energy suppliers
 Friends or colleagues
 Institutional news agencies
 Other (please specify)

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14. ACCEPTANCE

44. To what extent would you agree to install a small to medium size renewable energy production system in your property:

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly agree
for own consumption.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
for an organised form of shared consumption with the local community.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
to sell the extra amount to the general electricity grid.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

45. To what extent would you agree with the idea of installing a small to medium size renewable energy production plant in your town, village or neighborhood:

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly agree
to sell the extra amount to the general electricity grid and get a discount on your monthly bill.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
for the collective consumption of the local community.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

46. Please rank the proposed renewable energy production systems' options starting from your most favorite to the least favorite.

Small renewable energy production system in your property for private use.

Small renewable energy production system in your property for an organised form of shared consumption with the local community.

Small renewable energy production system in your property allowing to sell the extra amount to the network.

Small to medium size renewable energy production plant built in your town/village/neighborhood to sell energy to the general electricity grid and get a discount on your monthly bill.

Small to medium size renewable energy production plant built in your town/village/neighborhood for collective consumption by the local community.

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15. HOW DID YOU FIND US?

47. How did you receive this survey?

- I received the survey link from a colleague/friend.
- I found the survey link on social media.
- I found the survey link on the RENAISSANCE website.
- I received the survey link through the RENAISSANCE newsletter.
- I received the survey link through the BRIDGE initiative.
- None of the above (please specify)

48. Please specify your involvement in the RENAISSANCE project. Select the most appropriate among the following:

- I live in one of the pilot sites.
- I study in one of the pilot sites.
- I work in one of the pilot sites.
- I am a TSO/DSO representative involved in one of the pilot sites.
- I am an energy trading company representative involved in one of the pilot sites.
- I am an energy cooperative representative of one of the pilot sites.
- I am a local administration representative of one of the pilot sites.
- I am a member of the RENAISSANCE consortium.
- I am a member of the RENAISSANCE external stakeholders group.
- I am interested in the topic but not directly involved in the RENAISSANCE project.
- None of the above (please specify)

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16. THANK YOU

Thank you for taking the time to complete this survey. Your participation in this research is very much appreciated.

If you would like to hear about the RENAISSANCE project results or future project activities, please send us an email at info@renaissance-h2020.eu or subscribe to our Newsletter.

Please read carefully [Survey Monkey Privacy Policy](#) and the [RENAISSANCE project GDPR provisions](#).

On behalf of RENAISSANCE Consortium:

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